

Review on Compound Fabrics

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Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive review of compound fabrics, focusing on their structures, benefits, creation methods, and care considerations. Compound fabrics, synthesized from various structures, offer enhanced properties over single-component fabrics. The study outlines two primary structures employed in clothing fabrication: woven and knitted. Furthermore, it delves into the advantages of fabric compounding, elucidating synergistic properties, economical production, and weight reduction achieved through this process. The methods for creating compound fabric are discussed, encompassing lengthwise, widthwise, and layer wise compounding techniques. Moreover, the article highlights crucial care considerations during the stitching process, emphasizing seam balancing, precautions for stretchable fabrics, stability challenges, and techniques to prevent fraying and finish seams. By addressing these aspects, manufacturers and designers can optimize the performance and longevity of compound fabrics in various applications.

Keyword: Hybrid Structure, Knits, Layering, Synergistic Properties, Structure Compounding

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1. Introduction

Textile fabrics stand as a fundamental element interwoven into the daily lives of every individual on Earth, serving humanity for countless centuries. These materials exhibit commendable strength, flexibility, permeability, and drape properties, collectively contributing to the creation of fabrics that provide substantial protection, aesthetic appeal, and comfort when incorporated into various applications such as apparel and garments [1]. In the interest of crafting the right product, fabric properties play a pivotal role, and these properties can be finely tuned through several influencing factors. The selection of fibres, including options like cotton, polyester, viscose, nylon, and others. The selection of yarn, ranging from spun yarn, fancy yarn, textured yarn, to filament yarn. The selection of fabric's structural composition adds another layer of customization, with options such as woven, weft knitted, warp knitted and nonwoven. Furthermore, the selection of finish of the fabric through the application of various chemicals, completes the comprehensive process of tailoring textiles [2]. Therefore, it becomes evident that the properties of fibres, the structural composition of the fabric, and the application of finishes all contribute significantly to the end properties of the garment [3, 4]. The intricate interplay of fibre characteristics, fabric structure, and the incorporation of different yarns collectively define the ultimate attributes of the fabric, influencing its suitability and performance in the world of fashion and every day wear.

2. Structures Used for Clothing

The structural composition of fabric stands as a crucial determinant in influencing the overall performance, particularly in the state of maintaining the thermo-regulation of the human body through apparel. The selection of fabric structure becomes a strategic decision, intricately tied to the intended end use of the garment. Predominantly, woven, and knitted structures are the stalwarts in the textile industry, offering diverse characteristics. Woven and knitted fabrics, while both serving as fundamental pillars in textile manufacturing, exhibit distinct variations in their structural organization, thereby impacting their functional attributes. The utilization of woven structures involves the interlacement of warp and weft yarns, resulting in a fabric known for its durability, strength, and

dimensional stability. On the other hand, knitted fabrics are characterized by interlooping yarns, providing them with superior flexibility, elasticity, and drape. These inherent differences in structural arrangements contribute to the unique performance of each fabric type.

Figure 1 - Woven and Knitted Structure

The significance of fabric structure in thermo-regulation is underscored by the fact that the body's comfort is influenced by how efficiently the fabric allows for heat exchange. The choice between woven and knitted structures, or even nonwoven and braided structures, becomes pivotal in achieving the desired balance between insulation and breathability. This structural variability, as outlined by Özdil et al. [5], underscores the nuanced interplay between fabric structure and performance, serving as a guiding principle for textile engineers and designers aiming to optimize the functionality of garments for diverse end uses.

2.1 Woven Structure

In the intricate world of woven fabrics, the synergy of two or more sets of yarns intricately interlaced at right angles gives rise to a textile marvel. This unique interlacement creates a structured matrix, endowing woven fabrics with distinctive properties that set them apart in textile engineering. The meticulous choice of weave determines not only the aesthetic appeal of the fabric but also its inherent ability to resist creases and maintain a crisp appearance. Additionally, the woven structure manifests commendable stability under stress, offering a fabric that withstands various forces without compromising its integrity. This stability extends to the realm of air permeability, with denser woven fabrics displaying a lesser tendency to allow air passage, making them particularly suitable for specific applications.

Figure 2 - Basic Woven Fabric Weaves [6]

Furthermore, woven fabrics boast remarkable stability in normal use and care, showcasing minimal shrinkage, typically less than 2%. This minimal shrinkage contributes to the longevity and reliability of woven garments, ensuring that they maintain their original dimensions over time. The preference for woven structures extends to scenarios where heightened breaking strength, tearing resistance, dimensional stability, and specialized material requirements are paramount. In essence, the woven structure emerges as a stalwart choice in the textile landscape, embodying a harmonious blend of durability, stability, and versatility for applications ranging from everyday wear to specialized industrial uses.

2.2 Knitted Structure

In the intricate world of knitted structures, a fascinating interplay of interconnected loops takes center stage, crafted with either a single set or multiple sets of yarns. This method of construction gives rise to fabrics with unique characteristics that distinguish knitted textiles in the vast landscape of textile engineering. At the core of knitted fabrics lies their exceptional stretch and elasticity, a property that endows them with the ability to gracefully adapt to the dynamic movements of the human body, thereby ensuring unparalleled comfort and flexibility. A notable feature of knitted structures is the presence of open spaces between yarns, contributing to their inherent breathability and air permeability. This openness not only facilitates moisture regulation but also enhances the overall comfort level of garments fashioned from knitted fabrics. Another distinguishing quality of knitted textiles is their remarkable capacity to recover from wrinkles, presenting an advantage in terms of maintaining a smooth and neat appearance even after periods of wear. Moreover, these fabrics tend to exhibit higher shrinkage unless subjected to heat-setting processes.

Figure 3 - Basic Knits [6]

Despite these considerations, the preference for knitted structures remains strong in various applications due to their exceptional drape, moisture permeability, and overall comfort. As Choudhary and Goel [7] highlight, the unique attributes of knitted fabrics position them as the fabric of choice for those seeking a perfect blend of style, functionality, and ease of wear in diverse settings.

3. Meaning and Need of Compound Fabric

A compound material refers to a composite entity comprising two or more distinct things or substances harmoniously blended to form a cohesive whole. Similarly, in the realm of textiles, a compound fabric structure signifies the combination of two or more types of structures to create a unified product. Traditionally, a single structure is employed in the creation of a textile product, chosen based on the specific parameters and requirements dictated by the intended application. However, there are instances where a single structure may not fully meet all the desired criteria for a particular product, leading to the need for a more versatile solution – the compound fabric. The concept of compound fabric structures becomes invaluable when a product necessitates diverse structural attributes in different areas. For instance, a garment might require enhanced durability in certain regions while demanding superior crease recovery capabilities in others. The compound fabric structure offers a flexible and tailored approach to address these specific and often contrasting requirements within a single product. Combining different fabric structures, manufacturers can create textiles that exhibit a bespoke blend of properties, effectively solving the challenge of customizing products to meet multifaceted demands. This versatility is particularly advantageous in the textile industry, where diverse applications and performance criteria coexist. The compound fabric structure thus emerges as a strategic solution, allowing for the optimization of textile products to cater to the varied and nuanced needs of consumers and industries alike.

3.1 Benefits of Fabric compounding

3.1.1 Synergizing Properties

Fabric compounding, the combinations of two different types of fabrics, offers a unique advantage by synergizing their properties. When distinct fabrics are combined, their individual strengths can complement each other, resulting in a final fabric that exhibits a harmonious blend of desirable characteristics. For instance, if one fabric provides excellent durability but lacks in terms of softness, compounding it with another fabric that offers superior comfort can create a composite material that excels in both durability and softness. This synergy enhances the overall performance and functionality of the fabric, making it a versatile choice for various applications.

3.1.2 Economical Fabric Production

Fabric compounding is employed strategically to produce textiles that are not only versatile but also economical. By combining the aesthetic and comfort properties of one fabric with the structural or performance characteristics of another, manufacturers can create a fabric that meets specific requirements without compromising on cost-effectiveness.

3.1.3 Weight Reduction

Another significant benefit of fabric compounding is the ability to reduce the weight of the fabric without compromising its essential characteristics. Through a thoughtful combination of different fabrics, it becomes possible to create a composite material that retains all the desirable properties while being lighter in weight. This is particularly advantageous in industries where lightweight textiles are preferred, such as in sportswear or outdoor gear. The reduction in weight enhances the comfort and wearability of the fabric without sacrificing the integrity of its key attributes [8].

3.2 Ways to Create Compound Fabric

The process of fabric compounding unfolds through a countless of possibilities, exploring numerous permutations and combinations to achieve diverse textile outcomes. Even within the context of just two basic fabric structures, such as woven and weft-knitted structures, the potential for compounding expands significantly. In this scenario, compounding can occur in multiple dimensions, including length wise, width wise, and layer wise configurations, each yielding distinct fabric characteristics. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 visually represents the outcomes derived from the combination of woven and weft-knitted materials.

i. Lengthwise Compounding

In lengthwise compounding, the woven and weft-knitted structures are combined along the length of the fabric. This integration allows for the creation of fabrics with a continuous blend of characteristics spanning the entire length. The resulting textile may exhibit properties derived from both structures, offering a balanced combination of strength, flexibility, and other attributes along the length of the fabric.

Figure 4 - Lengthwise Compounding

ii. Width wise Compounding

Conversely, width wise compounding involves the incorporation of woven and weft-knitted structures across the width of the fabric. This lateral integration allows for the juxtaposition of the two structures side by side. The width wise compounding technique is advantageous in tailoring fabric properties to suit specific areas of the garment, contributing to a fabric with localized characteristics optimized for functions.

Figure 5 - Widthwise Compounding

iii. Layer wise Compounding

Layer wise compounding takes fabric complexity to another level by combining woven and weft-knitted structures in layers. Each layer contributes unique attributes, and the stacking of these layers creates a composite fabric with a multifaceted performance profile. This approach is particularly valuable in achieving a nuanced combination of properties such as insulation, moisture-wicking, and durability, layer by layer. Fig. 6 serves as a visual representation of the innovative possibilities arising from the combination of woven and weft-knitted materials.

Figure 6 - Layer wise Compounding

Through strategic compounding, fabric engineers can craft textiles that not only exhibit a harmonious fusion of structural elements but also cater to specific and customized requirements across different dimensions of the fabric. This approach underscores the versatility and adaptability offered by fabric compounding in tailoring textiles for diverse applications.

3.3 Factors to Fix at Compounding

The process of compounding woven, and knitted structures is not merely a union of materials but requires a meticulous optimization of various factors to ensure a seamless integration and enhance the overall performance of the fabric. Several critical considerations come into play during this optimization process, emphasizing the need for precision and expertise.

a). Seams and Stitches

Achieving a harmonious fusion between woven and knitted structures involves careful attention to seams and stitches at the joining points. The choice of stitching techniques and seam types becomes crucial to maintain the structural integrity of the compounded fabric. This optimization ensures that the transition between woven and knitted segments is smooth, minimizing any potential weaknesses at these interfaces.

b). Fabric Strip Length

In lengthwise and width wise compounding, the optimization of fabric strip length is paramount. The length of each strip must be calculated to facilitate a seamless integration of the woven and knitted structures. This optimization prevents uneven tension, distortion, or misalignment in the compounded fabric, contributing to a uniform and well-balanced product.

c). Thickness in layer wise Compounding

For layer wise compounding, where woven and knitted structures are combined in layers, optimizing the thickness of each layer is essential. This involves a precise control of the layer dimensions to achieve the desired overall

thickness of the compounded fabric. Striking the right balance ensures that the fabric meets specific requirements for applications such as insulation, moisture management, or comfort.

d). Thread Ticket Number and Needle Selection

The ticket number of the thread and the choice of needle are critical aspects of the optimization process. These elements impact the strength, flexibility, and overall quality of the stitched seams. Selecting an appropriate ticket number and needle type ensures that the compounded fabric maintains its structural integrity, with stitches that endure wear and tear while contributing to the fabric's overall performance.

By optimizing these parameters, fabric engineers and manufacturers can enhance the efficacy of compounded fabrics. The careful consideration of seams, strip lengths, thickness, thread characteristics, and needle selection collectively contributes to the creation of a fabric that not only combines woven and knitted structures effectively but also meets the specific performance requirements of the intended application. This optimization process underscores the precision and expertise required in achieving the desired outcomes in compounded fabric manufacturing.

4. Care to be Taken While Stitching Compound Fabric

4.1 Seam Balancing

A seam, defined as a joint created by stitching together two or more pieces of material, plays a pivotal role in determining the strength and efficiency of a fabric. Achieving balance in a seam is imperative to ensure optimal performance. In the context of compounding woven and knitted structures, maintaining seam equilibrium becomes even more critical due to the inherent differences in the characteristics of these materials.

4.2 Precautions for Stretchable Fabric

When stitching together woven and knitted structures with the same seam length, special precautions are warranted, particularly concerning the stretchability of knitted fabric. Knitted fabrics have the propensity to stretch, which can lead to defects such as seam puckering and waviness. To counteract this, a walking pressure foot, capable of stabilizing the seam, should be selected. If attaching a walking foot to the machine is unfeasible, preliminary testing at the raw fabric stage is advisable. The arrangement of knitted fabric on top of the woven, or vice versa, should be explored to mitigate potential stretching issues.

4.3 Addressing Stability Challenges

An additional challenge arises when the knitted fabric lacks sufficient stability to support the weight and drape of the woven fabric without undesirable pulling at the seam. This issue can be rectified by adding stabilization to the seam. Incorporating an elastic strip, matching the width of the bodice, along the seam provides additional structure, ensuring stability and preventing unattractive distortions.

4.4 Preventing Fraying and Finishing Seams

The combination of woven and knitted fabrics may introduce another concern – woven fabric fraying. Unlike knitted fabric, woven fabric is susceptible to fraying. To address this, it is imperative to finish the seam after stitching the fabrics together. Alternatively, finishing the edge of the woven fabric with pinking shears before stitching it to the knit serves as a preventive measure against fraying.

The compounding of woven and knitted structures requires a meticulous approach to seam construction. Balancing the seam for strength, addressing stretch-related challenges, ensuring stability, and preventing fraying are essential considerations. These precautions not only enhance the structural integrity of the compounded fabric but also contribute to the overall success of the manufacturing process [9].

5. Conclusion

Compound fabrics offer multifaceted benefits and versatile applications in textile engineering, outperforming single-component fabrics due to diverse fibre and structure synthesis. Understanding their structures, creation methods, and care is crucial. Adherence to proper stitching techniques and stability management ensures durability. Future research and innovation in fabric compounding will advance textile possibilities with enhanced properties.

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